

Kinetic analyses of thermogravimetric data of solid PCS up to 1673K in flowing Nitrogen

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Abstract

Pyrolysis kinetics of an indigenously developed solid PCS, a promising source of making SiC foams, have been investigated using TGA up to 1673K in N₂. Tests were performed at 5, 10 and 20K/min to assess the dependence of pyrolysis on heating rate. Primary decomposition of PCS was spanned over 430–1060K and the range shifted towards higher side at increased heating rate. On contrary, irrespective of heating rate, the PCS traced two distinct peaks in the DTG curves. While, the moderately low temperature peak (<750K) indicated loss of oligomers and water, the high temperature peak (≤950K) indicated loss of organic side groups and formation of inorganic state. To evaluate the Arrhenius parameters (E_a and A) of PCS pyrolysis, Coats-Redfern model was used. Comparatively slower reaction rate at low temperature regime with lower E_a (~50 kJ/mol) and higher rate during the second stage of pyrolysis having higher E_a (~120 kJ/mol) were obtained.

Key words: Polycarbosilane, TGA, Pyrolysis kinetics

